

Redox-mediated hybrid zinc-air flow batteries for more resilient integrated power systems - Grant Agreement Number 101115535

Deliverable D1.3 – Project Management Plan

Dissemination level

PU – Public	X
SEN – Sensitive; only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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Executive Summary

Deliverable 1.3 Project Management Plan summarizes important aspect of the ReZilient project. It comprises a Gantt chart with a work-breakdown structure including schedule, responsible partner, and related deliverables per WP and task, plus HSE issues and potential risks and measures taken to mitigate their impact. Together with the deliverable 1.2 “Project Management Handbook”, it provides a comprehensive guide and overview of the ReZilient project, its governance and management.

1 Background

ReZilient is a four-year project granted under the Horizon Europe topic HORIZON-EIC-2022-PATHFINDERCHALLENGES-01-02, with the overall goal to fill the gap between short-term electrochemical energy storage and long-term hydrogen storage by developing and demonstrating at lab-scale (0.5-1.5kW/6kWh) a completely new Zn-air flow battery technology.

1.1 List of partners

ReZilient has eight beneficiaries and three affiliated entities. Among the eight beneficiaries are six research institutions or universities, and two industrial companies. The partners are spread across Europe, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Geographical distribution of ReZilient partners

Full name and roles of ReZilient partners are given in Table 1.

Table 1: ReZilient partners

No.	Role	Short name	Full name
1	Coordinator	SER	SINTEF Energi AS
2	Beneficiary	SIN	SINTEF AS
3	Beneficiary	AU	AARHUS UNIVERSITET
4	Beneficiary	VBP	VISBLUE PORTUGAL
4.1	Affiliated	VB	VISBLUE APS
5	Beneficiary	TUD	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT
6	Beneficiary	UTU	TURUN YLIOPISTO
7	Beneficiary	AALTO	AALTO KORKEAKOULUSAATIO SR
8	Beneficiary	EZ	EVERZINC GROUP
8.1	Affiliated	EZB	EVERZINC BELGIUM
8.2	Affiliated	EZN	EVERZINC NEDERLAND B.V

2 Work Breakdown Structure

2.1 WP overview

An overview of ReZilient work packages (WP) and the lead partner is given in Table 2

Table 2: ReZilient Work Packages (WP) with lead partner

WP no.	WP name	Lead partner
1	Project Management, Communication, and Exploitation	SER
2	Zinc Electrode	TUD
3	Mediators and Catalysts	AU
4	Modelling	SER
5	TRL 4 Demonstration	VBP
6	Business Potential & Pilot Design	SIN
7	Portfolio management	SER

2.2 Gantt chart

Table 3 shows an overview of ReZilient work packages with subtasks and involved partners.

Table 3: ReZilient Gantt chart with work packages, subtasks and involved partners

Project work packages (WP) and tasks (T)	Partners involved	2023			2024				2025				2026				2027		
		Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3		
WP1 Project Management, Communication, and Exploitation																			
T1.1 Financial and administrative management	SER, all																		
T1.2 Coordination and project management	SER, all																		
T1.3 Establish data management plan	SER, all																		
T1.4 Communication and dissemination activities	SER, all																		
T1.5 Exploitation, standardisation, and IPR activities	SER, all																		
WP2 Zinc Electrode																			
T2.1 Zn electrode morphology/formulation/architecture	TUD, EZ, SER																		
T2.2 Additives for suppression of HER	TUD, AU																		
T2.3 Electrochemical Characterization of zinc morphologies	TUD, SER, AU																		
WP3 Mediators and Catalysts																			
T3.1 Screening of mediators for negative & positive side	UTU, Aalto, AU, TUD																		
T3.2 Synthesis and characterization of catalysts for mediated ORR and OER	AU, TUD, UTU																		
T3.3 Electrochemical testing of mediated zinc ox/red	AU, TUD, SER																		
WP4 Modelling																			
T4.1 Parametrisation	SER, TUD, AU																		
T4.2 Modelling of semi-solid electrode	TUD, SER, AU																		
T4.3 Modelling of porous solid electrode	SER, TUD, AU																		
T4.4 Full battery modelling	SER, TUD, VBP, AU																		
WP5 TRL 4 Demonstration																			
T5.1 Zn/ZnO and ORR/OER reactor design & construction	AU, SER, TUD, EZ																		
T5.2 Design & construction of demonstration system	VBP, AU, SER																		
T5.3 Upscaling of chemicals	AU, EZ, TUD																		
T5.4 Validation & Long-term testing	VBP, AU, SIN, SER																		
WP6 Business Potential & Pilot Design																			
T6.1 Economic Assessment / Macro-economic and Market analysis	SIN, EZ, VBP, SER																		
T6.2 Levelised Cost Assessment	VBP, SIN, SER																		
T6.3 Environmental screening and life cycle assessment	SIN, SER, VBP, EZ, AU																		
T6.4 Pilot Concept Design	VBP, SER, SIN																		
WP7 Portfolio management																			
T7.1 Portfolio management and project governance	SER																		
T7.2 Portfolio action plan	SER																		
T7.3 Portfolio actions to foster innovation	SER																		
T7.4 Implementation of portfolio dissemination and exploitation activities	SER																		
T7.5 Techno-economic benchmark and comparative assessment	SER																		

2.3 Deliverables

Figures 2- 4 shows a graphical representation of the timeline of ReZilient deliverables and milestones, split into the three reporting periods. The various colours denote the WP responsible for the deliverables (milestones shown in black).

Figure 2: ReZilient deliverables Reporting Period 1

Figure 3: ReZilient deliverables and milestones Reporting Period 2

Figure 4: ReZilient deliverables and milestones reporting period 3

The corresponding Table 4 gives more details on the deliverables.

Table 4: ReZilient deliverables. Type: R=report, DMP=Data Management Plan, DEM=Demonstration. Dissemination level: PU=Public, SEN=Sensitive. Due month is given as project months.

Deliv. No	Work Package No	Deliverable Name	Description	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissem. Level	Due month
D1.1	WP1	Website and project logo	Website and project logo information with also social media links	SER	R	PU	2
D1.2	WP1	Project Management Handbook	Handbook summarizes all the information required for an optimum management of ReZilient	SER	R	PU	3
D7.1	WP7	Portfolio Action Plan	The deliverable will contain the initial Portfolio Action Plan. The progress on implementation of activities and any required modifications will be reflected in the annual deliverables "Report on portfolio activities"	SER	R	SEN	4
D1.3	WP1	Project Management Plan	Governing tool comprising a Gantt chart with a work-breakdown structure including a schedule per task, responsible partner, related subtasks, related deliverables, dependencies on other tasks, plus HSE issues and potential risks and measures taken to mitigate their impact.	SER	R	PU	6
D1.5	WP1	Data Management Plan	A DMP will be established and revised throughout the lifetime of the project to present the status of the project's reflections on data management.	SER	DMP	PU	6
D1.8	WP1	Plan for Dissemination and Communication Activities	A C&D plan will be established, with a first version in M6. This will be updated with a new version in M48	SER	R	PU	6
D1.10	WP1	Plan for Exploitation Activities	A detailed plan for sustainable exploitation and a description of possible business models and IPR approaches for the outcomes. First version by M6 and final plan for exploitation beyond the project period in M48	SER	R	SEN	6
D3.1	WP3	Mediators A	Catalogue of mediators characterised in project – decision tool for which mediators to use	AU	R	SEN	12
D7.2	WP7	Y1 Report on portfolio activities	The report will present the portfolio activities that have been carried out in each reporting period and contain relevant material (e.g. PowerPoint presentations, minutes of meetings, etc.). It also explains how the portfolio activities and the EIC proactive project management approach contribute to the achievement of the project objectives and help the transition to market. In addition it describes the roadmap of actions and synergies to be undertaken during the next year.	SER	R	SEN	12
D1.12	WP1	RP1 review meeting	Documents related to the review meetings RP1, RP2, RP3 (expected timing M14, M32, M49)	SER	R	SEN	13
D1.4	WP1	Revised Project Management Plan	Governing tool comprising a Gantt chart with a work-breakdown structure including a schedule per task, responsible partner, related subtasks, related deliverables, dependencies on other tasks, plus HSE issues and potential risks and measures taken to mitigate their impact.	SER	R	PU	18
D2.1	WP2	Zn architecture A	Catalogue of architectures characterized in project. Decision tool for which architecture to use	TUD	R	SEN	18
D2.3	WP2	HER suppression additive A	Catalogue of additive characterised in project – decision tool for which additive to use	TUD	R	SEN	18
D3.3	WP3	Catalysts A	Catalogue of catalysts characterised in project – decision tool for which catalysts to use	TUD	R	SEN	18
D4.1	WP4	Parametrisation	Report on model parametrisation	SER	R	PU	18
D2.5	WP2	Zn electrode performance A	Electrochemical and physical characterization of zinc morphologies	TUD	R	SEN	24
D3.2	WP3	Mediators B	Catalogue of mediators characterised in project – decision tool for which mediators to use	AU	R	SEN	24

D7.3	WP7	Y2 Report on portfolio activities	The report will present the portfolio activities that have been carried out in each reporting period and contain relevant material (e.g. PowerPoint presentations, minutes of meetings, etc.). It also explains how the portfolio activities and the EIC proactive project management approach contribute to the achievement of the project objectives and help the transition to market. In addition it describes the roadmap of actions and synergies to be undertaken during the next year.	SER	R	SEN	24
D7.6	WP7	Technologies potentials assessment	Individual project contribution to a joint report with other project in the portfolio on the key factors affecting the penetration of the proposed technologies in each market segment and the relative competitiveness of each solution in different end user applications.	SER	R	SEN	24
D1.6	WP1	RP2 update of the Data Management Plan	A DMP will be established and revised throughout the lifetime of the project to present the status of the project's reflections on data management.	SER	DMP	PU	30
D2.2	WP2	Zn architecture B	Catalogue of architectures characterized in project. Decision tool for which architecture to use	TUD	R	SEN	30
D2.4	WP2	HER suppression additive B	Catalogue of additive characterised in project – decision tool for which additive to use	TUD	R	SEN	30
D3.4	WP3	Catalysts B	Catalogue of catalysts characterised in project – decision tool for which catalysts to use	TUD	R	SEN	30
D4.2	WP4	Semi-solid electrode	Report on optimal particle size distribution in the semi-solid electrode	TUD	R	PU	30
D4.3	WP4	Porous solid electrode	Report on optimal morphology of the porous solid electrode	SER	R	PU	30
D5.1	WP5	Chemicals for demonstration	Mediators, catalysts and Zn/ZnO electrodes for TRL4 demonstration	AU	DEM	SEN	30
D1.13	WP1	RP2 review meeting	Documents related to the review meetings RP1, RP2, RP3 (expected timing M14, M32, M49)	SER	R	SEN	31
D2.6	WP2	Zn electrode performance B	Electrochemical and physical characterization of zinc morphologies	TUD	R	SEN	36
D4.4	WP4	Battery model	Open-source full battery model software available on GitLab	SER	OTHER	PU	36
D5.2	WP5	Reactors	Reactors for TRL4 demonstration	TUD	DEM	SEN	36
D6.1	WP6	Market analysis	An overview of the customers and competitors and an initial quantification of the market size	SIN	R	SEN	36
D6.3	WP6	LCA analysis	A comparative environmental life cycle analysis (LCA) providing the environmental impact of the ReZilient. The analysis includes the climate change potential and ecotoxicity potential	SIN	R	PU	36
D7.4	WP7	Y3 Report on portfolio activities	The report will present the portfolio activities that have been carried out in each reporting period and contain relevant material (e.g. PowerPoint presentations, minutes of meetings, etc.). It also explains how the portfolio activities and the EIC proactive project management approach contribute to the achievement of the project objectives and help the transition to market. In addition it describes the roadmap of actions and synergies to be undertaken during the next year.	SER	R	SEN	36
D5.4	WP5	Demonstration system	TRL4 demonstration system	VB	DEM	SEN	38
D6.2	WP6	LCOS analysis	Estimation of the levelized cost of storage for mid- and long-duration energy storage, including cost of electricity	VBP	R	PU	42
D5.3	WP5	Upscaling	Report for upscaling of zinc, catalysts, mediators	AU	R	SEN	44
D1.7	WP1	RP3 update of the Data Management Plan	A DMP will be established and revised throughout the lifetime of the project to present the status of the project's reflections on data management.	SER	DMP	PU	48
D1.9	WP1	Final version of Plan for Dissemination and	A C&D plan will be established, with a first version in M6. This will be updated with a new version in M48	SER	R	PU	48

		Communication Activities					
D1.11	WP1	Final version of Plan for Exploitation Activities	A detailed plan for sustainable exploitation and a description of possible business models and IPR approaches for the outcomes. First version by M6 and final plan for exploitation beyond the project period in M48	SER	R	SEN	48
D1.14	WP1	RP3 review meeting	Documents related to the review meetings RP1, RP2, RP3 (expected timing M14, M32, M49)	SER	R	SEN	48
D5.5	WP5	ReZilient cell test results	Report on the results and performance of the mZAFB developed in ReZilient	VBP	R	SEN	48
D6.4	WP6	Pilot Concept design	The results of the demonstration will feed into the pilot design which will be implemented after the project duration	VBP	R	SEN	48
D7.5	WP7	Y4 Report on portfolio activities	The report will present the portfolio activities that have been carried out in each reporting period and contain relevant material (e.g. PowerPoint presentations, minutes of meetings, etc.). It also explains how the portfolio activities and the EIC proactive project management approach contribute to the achievement of the project objectives and help the transition to market. In addition it describes the roadmap of actions and synergies to be undertaken during the next year.	SER	R	SEN	48
D7.7	WP7	Final version of technologies potentials assessment	Individual project contribution to a joint report with other project in the portfolio on the key factors affecting the penetration of the proposed technologies in each market segment and the relative competitiveness of each solution in different end user applications.	SER	R	SEN	48

3 Risks, risk mitigation and HSE

3.1 Risk monitoring and evaluation

The risk management in ReZilient will follow SINTEF’s certified quality management system (in accordance with ISO 9001:2015, ISO 14001:2015 and ISO 45001:2018.), adopted to manage project issues and conflicts. The plan will contribute to the monitoring of the project based on a dynamic and iterative process outlined in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Risk management process

ReZilient has established a procedure for monitoring and evaluation of project risks through the project management team. All project risks are followed up monthly through the ReZilient risk matrix, evaluating any changes to the probability or consequences of the risks. At the start of the project, the ReZilient risk matrix is shown in Figure 6.

Risks:

Critical risks	No. Type	Name
	1 Technical	Identification of mediators for ZnO/Zn redox fails
	2 Technical	ZnO/Zn get into the stack (either particles or dissolved as ions) and electroplating in the cell
	3 Technical	Not efficient Non-PGM catalysts for ORR
	4 Technical	Mediators for ORR cannot be identified
	5 Technical	Mediators/catalyst for OER cannot be identified

Figure 6: ReZilient risk matrix with identified critical risks

All risks have identified type of risk and potential consequences in terms of costs, delays, reputation, environment, health and other factors, as well as counter measures and next actions to be taken. Details on risk identification is shown in Figure 7.

	Explanation	Example
Risk name	Name/identifier for the risk	Resource allocation
WPs concerned	Which WPs are affected by the risk?	All WPs
Risk period	Use project months	M1-M48
Description	Describe the risk, the issue it is linked to	Risk of lacking key personnel due to holidays, sickness or other leaves, other priorities or similar.
Type of risk	Technical, Management, Societal/Political, or other.	Technical
Impact	Low, medium-low, medium, medium-high, high	Medium
Probability	Low, medium-low, medium, medium-high, high	Medium
Potential consequences (costs, delays, reputation, environmental, health, etc)	Describe consequences if risk occurs. Think in terms of costs, delay, reputation, environmental, health, etc.	Potential delays in work and deliverables. Potentially added costs for training of additional personnel
Counter measures	Describe counter measures/mitigation actions: Prevention: Elimination of risk by doing things differently. Reduction: Changing procedures/work in order to reduce impact or probability to acceptable levels Contingency: Pre planned actions that start when the Risk manifests. Acceptance: In extraordinary cases one have to accept the risk. If Probability or Consequence is Medium or higher, this has to be approved by the Coordinator	Good communication on potential issues in PMT meetings. Routines for storing project data for easy findability.
Next action including deadline and responsible	Actions to be undertaken. Include deadline and responsible	On the agenda for PMT meetings (15.3.2024; R Sæterli)
Responsible	Responsible partner/ person to ensure counter measures and actions are followed up	Ragnhild Sæterli, SER
Current status	Open/Closed	Open
Comment		
Author	Risk described by	Ragnhild Sæterli
Date raised		22.01.2024
Date last updated		22.02.2024

Figure 7: ReZilient risk identification and follow up

3.2 Critical risks

Five critical risks with corresponding counter measures have been identified in ReZilient:

No.	Type	Name	Counter measures
1	Technical	Identification of mediators for ZnO/Zn redox fails	Demonstration in WP5 will be done with a non-mediated reaction for the negative side
2	Technical	ZnO/Zn get into the stack (either particles or dissolved as ions) and electroplating in the cell	Ions: mediators with very low zinc solubility will be screened to avoid Zn ions travelling to the stack and electroplating zinc. Particles: developing strategies to minimise effects (e.g.regular cleaning of stack).
3	Technical	Not efficient non-PGM catalysts for ORR	ORR catalyst for demonstration in WP5 will be based on platinum black
4	Technical	Mediators for ORR cannot be identified	Mediator for ORR in demonstration in WP5 will be done with an alternative solution
5	Technical	Mediators/catalyst for OER cannot be identified	Demonstration in WP5 will be done with OER in stack with nickel electrodes

3.3 Unforeseen risks

The ReZilient risk monitoring tool will also be used in case of unforeseen risks arising through the project period, and they followed up in the same manner as the critical risks.

3.4 HSE

All partners have an individual responsibility for HSE and ethics, and need to follow the Grant Agreement (GA), Consortium Agreement (CA), and their own rules regarding HSE work and issues.

Partners will

- ensure that their employers have the necessary skills for the planned work. Special training should be documented.
- ensure that employers and relevant equipment are fully insured.
- report immediately all serious near-incidents and real incidents that occur, directly to the Coordinator

The **project coordinator** is responsible for

- establishing routines to ensure that HSE is carried out in compliance with GA and CA, and all relevant statutory obligations
- reporting nonconformities to the General Assembly/consortium partners, and deciding which nonconformities that demands immediate alarming and actions
- reporting HSE deviations to the General Assembly

WP leaders will

- address HSE in coordination meetings with the staff working in the WP
- ensure that HSE requirements are addressed during planning and implementation of each WP
- ensure that activities in each WP has been the subject of a risk assessment whenever relevant
- report nonconformities in accordance with this plan

3.4.1 Risk assessments

The all personnel in ReZilient must make sure that potential hazards are identified, risks assessed, and that relevant plans are prepared and action taken to reduce risk.

A *risk assessment* should be carried out prior to the start of work operations which have not previously been subject to risk assessment. This commonly applies in situations where new or modified work processes and/or equipment are involved. Use of *safe-job-analysis* is encouraged on individual operations are not sufficient addressed in the risk assessment.

Risk assessment shall be carried out for the following activities within the ReZilient project:

- New activities in the laboratory
- Fieldwork
- Travel to countries outside the EU/EEA, the USA or Canada

Partners are free to use their own assessment forms, but the Coordinator will provide forms/methodology when required.

3.4.2 Unwanted incident

ReZilient partners will follow the health, safety and environmental conduct and procedures of their respective institutions. In case of unwanted incidents related to the project either directly or indirectly (i.e., that will affect the work in the project), ReZilient has established a procedure to report the incident and evaluate and follow up potential consequences for the project and minimize the risk of similar incidents. A flow chart of the process is shown in Figure 8. The Coordinator keeps track of incidents and reports to the GA either immediately or at the next GA meeting.

Figure 8: Flow diagram of unwanted incidents process

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